

ADVANTAGES OF TOTAL PHYSICAL RESPONSE METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the essential features of the TPR method. The advantages are also emphasized and the fact that the TPR method is the best for use in the classroom when teaching a foreign language. In this article, we see a vivid example of the influence of this method on the process of learning a language.

Key words: TPR, teaching method, young learners

Аннотация: Это статья посвящена рассмотрению некоторых существенных особенностей метода TPR. Также подчеркиваются плюсы и то что TPR метод лучший для использования в класса при обучении иностранному языку. В данной статье мы видим яркий пример влияния этого метода на процесс изучения языка.

Ключевые слова: TPR, преподавание, метод, молодые ученики

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola TPR usulining ba'zi muhim xususiyatlarini ko'rib chiqishga bag'ishlangan. Chet tilini o'rgatishda TPR usulining afzalliklari va sinfda qo'llash eng yaxshisi ekanligi ham ta'kidlangan. Ushbu maqolada biz ushbu uslubning tilni o'rganish jarayoniga ta'sirining yorqin misolini ko'ramiz.

Kalit so'zlar: TPR, o'qitish, metod, yosh o'quvchilar

Introduction

Total Physical Response (TPR) is a method of teaching a foreign or second language (target language) by developing listening comprehension through a series of commands to which students respond with physical activity. It was founded by James Asher, a professor of psychology, in the late 1960's and is still considered and used as a valuable linguistic tool in teaching a target language, especially in initial stages of instruction. It combines language and gesture, thus making language acquisition more natural and memorable (Asher 2007; Curtain and Dahlberg 2010; Larsen-Freeman 2004; Morley 2001). Learners are not expected to speak while performing actions, which makes TPR stress-free and suitable for teaching beginners, either young learners, teenagers or adults (Asher 2007).

How TPR works: In essence, the TPR method is the memorization of new words or phrases using gestures or performing commands from a teacher. For example,

the word ball — the ball, the children depict a gesture, as if playing with the ball, the word pen — pen — they pretend to write an imaginary pen, etc. In order to memorize a new word to a child, it is necessary to relate this word to its image — an object, a picture or a gesture, in which TPR helps us. Therefore, translation is not necessary and even harmful to use — for the time being, abstract-logical thinking has not been developed. Initially, the method was developed for different age categories, but, for obvious reasons, it took root only in teaching young learners. It is great for young learners to use TPR elements in combination with other methods in English lessons.

Learning new concepts through the body helps children understand the meaning without the teacher's explanation or translation. Such learning can easily be assessed by giving commands in new, unpredictable sequences and observing how fast and confidently children respond to them. It is very important that the teacher should not give any commands that can embarrass children. However, introducing funny commands is usually greatly appreciated by children, like in this example: Walk, walk, walk. Walk to the left, walk to the right. Drink, drink, drink. Drink to the left, drink to the right. Even giving outrageous commands, such as Put your elbow on the ceiling, can be useful in strengthening children's understanding of what is possible/impossible (Curtain and Dahlberg 2010, 64).

In modern school, the method of full physical response, as a rule, is not used, however, we believe that it will be the most effective in teaching the language of primary school students. We believe that this method can not only improve the quality of education, but also increase the motivation to learn a foreign language.

By applying the TPR method in schools, with young learners, we learned about several advantages of the TPR method.:

- 1) It is a lot of fun. Learners enjoy it, and this method can be a real stirrer in the class. It lifts the pace and the mood;
- 2) It is very memorable. It does assist students to recognize phrases or words;
- 3) It is good for kinaesthetic learners who are required to be active in the class.
- 4) It is very effective with teenagers and young learners; and
- 5) It involves both left and right-brained learning:

Conclusion: Summing up, we want to say that the TPR method is very effective in teaching young learners. The method is good in that it is a game in itself, and the teacher does not need to prepare in advance different games for the lesson in a special way. Also, in the TPR method, children are very interested, they not only

sit in the classroom, but draw, constantly move, gesticulate. And we also learned that this is very motivating for young learners in learning a foreign language.

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